

Early Byzantine Asceticism

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Holy men (θεῖος ἀνὴρ, also called men, servants, friends or devotees of God) emerged in the East as early as Late Antiquity and the Early Byzantine period. These were individuals that were thought to have been specifically chosen by God so as to spread his word and make him and his intentions present and evident to their contemporaries. In order to come closer to him and gain virtue and purity, holy men abandoned their previous life and practiced repentance and self-mortification through prayer and ascetic labour. As they needed to be undistracted to achieve this intimacy with God, holy men withdrew in isolation and lived in social disengagement. This explains their emergence mostly in Syria, due to the area's geography and climate. In the Syrian desert, as opposed to that of Egypt, these ascetics had the chance to dissociate themselves from the rest of the world and, at the same time, to survive in a relatively "friendly" environment, where they could more easily find adequate sources such as water and roots, even if they had to constantly be on the move. Consequently, they were able to completely cut themselves off from civilisation, while in the harsher landscape of Egypt they would have to carry with them, and then replicate, the well-known practices and habits of the nearby villages, making the contrast between the two worlds (that in a settled land and that in isolation) less apparent. So holy men left their cities, donated their possessions (which sometimes were many as some of them came from relatively wealthy families) to the poor, cut all ties with, and obligations towards, society, and started a new life without the support of family or friends. In addition, having reached a point where they did not have the same needs as other, "ordinary", people even on a physical level, they also managed to live in the open or sometimes in natural shelters in the desert and other barren or abandoned places, fasting or eating only raw vegetables and roots, and, for long periods, staying sleepless and often with no clothes except for a simple shirt. Following this way of life was of course not always easy, and they had to strive in order to complete their mission. During their isolation, they spent their time praying, trying to support themselves by the work of their hands, exercising their body and trying to control the elements of nature as well as their own bodies and passions through hard training (askesis), mortification and voluntary suffering, which can be seen as imitating the passion of Christ, in an attempt to rise above their human existence. It should be noted, however, that holy men did not consider the body itself to be evil, and what they tried to overcome and work against were the human weaknesses. Finally, although not usually mentioned in our sources, the lives of some of them must have been seriously threatened and even lost while practicing asceticism. A substitute death, such as living in a grave-like enclosed space, nonetheless, was a sign of holiness and the ultimate proof that the holy man was now something more than an "ordinary" person and had moved beyond the normal human condition. Although holy men started their askesis by contemplating in isolation, the crowd played a significant part in their lives. Many people would follow them, become their disciples and often form groups or even structured communities with permanent facilities around them, while others would travel long distances to visit them as pilgrims and ask for their help. Ascetics themselves also paid visits to each other and sometimes to nearby villages or cities where they offered their help and, if necessary, they could get a few supplies in exchange for simple repairs. Furthermore, some of them were often asked by the official church to take on positions in the church hierarchy, which they seldom did and only temporarily. Holy men were always ready to participate in the daily life of common people and the social elite in order to protect and integrate that life. However, it was not uncommon for people to be suspicious of them and accuse them of fraud, sorcery and other serious crimes (e.g. murder), even of woes that the community would face in periods of crisis, and holy men had to try to allay them. The crowd was an essential element in holy men's lives for an additional reason. Despite their initial withdrawal from the society, after achieving sanctity they

had to display signs of it, and the people were the audience they needed in order to exhibit their supernatural powers, as well as those who watched them closely, since they in fact expected to see the evidence that would prove the ascetics' holiness. Moreover, since holy men sometimes depended on patrons and their gifts and donations, they had to perform miracles for their sake when they were asked to do so. Hagiographers used to place much emphasis on specific incidents from their protagonists' lives in order to show their powers, such as blessing and cursing, praying or successfully interceding on behalf of their fellow citizens or even strangers who would ask for their help, and the power of prophecy. The most common sign, however, was that of healing, as holy men were thought to possess the ability to cure a variety of illnesses, both mental and physical. Most of the times they would pray for the sick person or visit them and cure them by touching them, while on other occasions they could send them one of their objects, which had acquired its owner's supernatural powers. Furthermore, as many such stories were based on that of Christ from the Gospels, occasionally holy men were presented as bringing a dead person back to life. The relation between the two can also be seen in the second most often proof of the ascetics' holiness, the conflict with devil. Holy men constantly had to deal with demons who stood in their way, and often had to heal people who had been possessed by such creatures by performing exorcisms. Their victory over these powers was certain, as they "represented" God, who had given them the ability to handle situations like that. The same is true for encounters with devil himself, who wanted to tempt holy men, distract them from their duties and prevent them from following an ascetic lifestyle. Usually he would do so by reminding them of their previous life they had left behind and all the sacrifices they had made, but the holy men were strong enough to resist him and, eventually, defeat him. Lastly, one should briefly also mention the role holy men played in society. The Syrian villages where they first emerged were, at the time, experiencing a decomposition of certain social institutions and a crisis of leadership, and were thus in need of a figure of authority. Therefore, for their inhabitants, holy men assumed the role of powerful rural patrons who would assist them in various aspects of their lives, both in everyday problems and in periods of crisis, while, at the same time, they were more accessible to them than actual patrons. As strangers who were not in any way related to the locals, they also played the role of objective mediators in rural life and sometimes even that of advisors, who reconciled and counselled villagers. Being at the centre of a prayer community as their spiritual fathers, they also offered petitions to God on their behalf, and these people, taking the holy men's ascetic lifestyle into account, were assured that the latter were close to God and he would therefore hear their prayers. Of course holy men were also considered to be representatives of God, and were thus famous amongst people both in the countryside and in the cities, where they often acquired wealthy patrons themselves. These officials, members of the court or the army and even emperors, assisted and supported them in any way possible and contributed to the rise of their reputation, in exchange for the ascetics' spiritual guidance and intercession with God. This relationship, as well as the one between holy men and the church authority, was not usually sought after by holy men themselves, who did not accept any offices. However, they gradually moved closer to the ecclesiastical hierarchy, and therefore they also started moving to Constantinople. Finally, it seems that sometimes holy men could work against authorities, namely the emperors, if the latter were usurpers or heretics, in which case the ascetics were regarded as a symbol of opposition to any kind of heresy. In any case, by overcoming their human existence and reaching the apogee of Christian morality, they soon became well-known and an essential part of everyday life in the Byzantine Empire.

Date Range: 400 CE - 600 CE

Region: Eastern Mediterranean

Region tags: Syria, Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean, Anatolia, Byzantium

Near East in Late Antiquity and the Early Byzantine period

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Brown, P. “The Rise and Function of the Holy Man in Late Antiquity.” *The Journal of Roman Studies* 61 (1971): 80-101.
- Source 2: Brown, P. “Holy Men.” In *The Cambridge Ancient History. Volume 14: Late Antiquity: Empire and Successors, AD 425-600*, edited by A. Cameron, B. Ward-Perkins, and M. Whitby, 781-810. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011.
- Source 3: Browning, R. (1981). The ‘Low Level’ Saint’s Life in the Early Byzantine World. In: S. Hackel, ed., *The Byzantine Saint*, London: Fellowship of St Alban and St Sergius, pp. 117-127.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Assigned when living mostly in the desert or other barren places under rather harsh circumstances in order to overcome the human existence and reach the apogee of Christian morality.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Holy men's corpses might be considered to have supernatural powers.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Worship of saints etc.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes

↳ Adultery:
– Yes

- ↳ Incest:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Holy men withdrew in isolation and lived in social disengagement, and therefore they abstained from any sexual activities.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Notes: Holy men were going through hard training (askesis), mortification and voluntary suffering, e.g. by carrying heavy chains or wrapping cords around their bodies.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Holy men donated their possessions (which sometimes were many as some of them came from relatively wealthy families) to the poor.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Holy men often acquired wealthy patrons, officials, members of the court or the army and even emperors, who assisted and supported them in exchange for the ascetics' spiritual guidance and intercession with God. This relationship, as well as the one between holy men and the church authority, was not usually sought after by holy men themselves, who did not accept any offices. However, they gradually moved closer to the ecclesiastical hierarchy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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